

Complexation of Osmium with 2-Mercapto-1-Substituted-4,4,6-Trimethyl 1H 4H Pyrimidines

AJAI K. SINGH and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110007

and

MOHAN KATYAL

St. Stephen's College, Delhi-110007

Manuscript received 14 January 1976; accepted 27 April 1976

Alkyl and aryl substituted 4, 4, 6-trimethyl (1H 4H)-2-pyrimidinethiols react selectively with osmium forming pinkish-red complexes (λ_{\max} 530–40 nm) extractable in *n*-butanol. The optimum conditions for the complexation have been established. Beer's law is obeyed and all the complexes contain osmium and pyrimidinethiol in 1:2 molar ratio. The effect of diverse ions in the determination of osmium has also been investigated.

FASCINATED by the analytical potentialities¹⁻⁵ of 2-mercapto benzimidazole it was thought worthwhile to investigate the similar aspects of 2-mercapto pyrimidines. In the course of study, it is found that 2-mercapto-1-substituted-4, 4, 6-trimethyl (1H 4H) pyrimidines (I-VI) react selectively with palladium and osmium in highly acidic medium. A highly selective method⁶ for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium with these pyrimidinethiols has already been reported. In the present paper the results of its complexation with osmium and subsequent spectrophotometric determination of the metal, are reported

- (I) R = H ; (II) R = C₂H₅ ; (III) R = *n*-C₄H₉ ;
(IV) R = C₆H₅ ; (V) R = C₆H₄OCH₃ (anisyl) ;
(VI) R = *p*-C₆H₄NO₂.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents: A Unicam SP 600 Spectrophotometer was used for the absorbance measurements.

Standard solution of osmium (VIII) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of OsO₄ (Johnson Mathey) in 0.2*N* sodium hydroxide. The solution was standardised by standard method before use.

2-Mercapto-1-substituted-4, 4, 6-trimethyl 1H 4H pyrimidines (I-VI) were prepared by the method of Mathes⁷ and their standard solutions (0.01*M* in concentration) were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amounts in 0.2*N* hydrochloric acid. All other solutions were prepared from analytical grade chemicals and deionized water.

Procedure for the determination of osmium: To a suitable aliquot of osmium solution (Table 1), add 3-4 ml of 5.0*N* hydrochloric acid and 5.0 ml of pyrimidinethiol solution (0.01 *M* in 0.2 *N* hydrochloric acid). Allow to stand the mixture for 45 min. Dilute to 10.0 ml, add 10.0 ml of *n*-butanol and shake for about

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF OSMIUM—COMPLEXES WITH 2-PYRIMIDINETHIOLS

Characteristics	Osmium—complex with pyrimidinethiol					
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
ϵ_{\max} , 1 mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	6600	8000	8600	7000	8200	9000
Acid concentration for maximum complexation	1.0–3.0 <i>N</i> HCl ; H ₂ SO ₄ ; HClO ₄ and HNO ₃	0.5–4.0 <i>N</i>	HCl ; H ₂ SO ₄ ; HClO ₄ and HNO ₃			
Molar excess of the 2-pyrimidinethiols needed for full colour development	15 times	15 times	15 times	15 times	15 times	15 times
Beer's law range (μ g/ml)	upto 28.5	upto 25.0	upto 23.0	upto 22.0	upto 19.5	upto 18.0
Optimum range of determination (μ g/ml)	5.0–22.0	5.0–21.0	5.2–20.0	5.8–19.0	5.2–18.0	5.0–16.0
Sandell's sensitivity	0.0288	0.0237	0.022	0.027	0.0231	0.021
Standard deviation from 8 samples	0.0050	0.0064	0.0082	0.0078	0.0046	0.0065

15 min. Allow to settle, remove the organic layer and measure its absorbance at 530-40 nm against a *n*-butanol blank. Calculate the metal concentration by comparing with a precalibrated graph.

Results and Discussion

Spectral characteristics : Solutions of all pyrimidinethiols except that of VI are colourless with negligible absorption in the visible region. However, the absorption by the light yellow coloured solution of the thiol VI is significant in this region. When few drops of any of the pyrimidinethiol solution (in 0.2 *N* HCl) were added to acidic osmium solution, bluish-red colouration resulted immediately. These bluish-red complexes were partially extractable in non-polar organic solvents *viz.* chloroform, benzene and carbontetrachloride where as in *n*-butanol, isobutanol and *iso*-amyl alcohol the complexes were completely extractable. *n*-Butanol was employed in subsequent studies because of its poor solubility in water. The minimum time for complete extraction was found to be 10 min. Just after the formation, all these complexes exhibited maximum absorption at 560-70 nm in *n*-butanol medium, but on keeping for about half an hour λ_{max} . Shifted to 530-40 nm absorbance remained constant and maximum at this wavelength for atleast 24 hr. Subsequent studies were, therefore, made at this wavelength. An identical behaviour was also observed in aqueous medium. The optimum conditions for the spectrophotometric determination and other optical constants are summarized in Table 1. It may be observed from the data in the table that there is a slight increase in sensitivity with increase in molecular weight of the ligand in alkyl (I-III) or aryl (IV-VI) substituted compounds.

Composition : Molar composition of the complexes was established by the methods of continuous variations and logarithmic. All the complexes contain osmium and pyrimidinethiol in 1 : 2 molar ratio.

Interferences : In the determination of 9.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of osmium, the following ions did not interfere to the extents ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) given in parentheses : F^- (10) ; Cl^- , Br^- or I^- (2000) ; NO_2^- (50) ; NO_3^- (2000) ; PO_4^{3-} or BO_3^{3-} (2000) ; $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (2000) ; $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ (1000) ; cit. or tart (2000) ; CH_3COO^- (2000) ; SCN^- or E.D.T.A. (1000) ; Cu^{2+} (10) ; Ni^{2+} or Co^{2+} (20) ; Zn^{2+} or Cd^{2+} (125) ; Fe^{3+} (25) ; Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} or Ba^{2+} (100) ; Sn^{2+} (25) ; Al^{3+} (100) ; Ti^{4+} or Zr^{4+} (100) ; V^{4+} (10) ; Au^{3+} (10) ; Pt^{4+} or Ru^{3+} (30) ; Rh^{3+} or Ir^{3+} (50). Ag^+ and Hg^{2+} , after masking with Cl^- and I^- respectively, did not interfere upto 15.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The presence of Pd^{2+} (5) could also be tolerated if 100 times molar excess of the ligand was used. However, the anion CN^- and thiourea should be absent.

Comparison with 2-mercapto benzimidazole reveals that 2-pyrimidinethiols are comparable in selectivity but lack in sensitivity.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R. (India) for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (A.K.S.)

References

1. F. E. BEAMISH, *Talanta*, 1965, 12, 743, 789.
2. A. K. MAJUMDAR and M. M. CHAKRABARTY, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1958, 162, 96.
3. J. G. SEN GUPTA, *Talanta*, 1961, 8, 729.
4. J. XAVIER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1958, 164, 250.
5. B. C. BERA and M. M. CHAKRABARTY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1966, 38, 1419.
6. A. K. SINGH, A. M. BHATTI and R. P. SINGH, Presented at the annual convention of chemists, 1975, Roorkee (India).
7. R. A. MATHES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1747.